

Covid – 19's Impact on Jobs and Job Market

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Abstract

The pandemic because of Covid-19 having short term and long terms and affects in the society, especially with regard to availability and sustainability of jobs and largely on job market. With intent to understand the patterns, ups and down of the current job market, Covid – 19 and its impact on jobs, economies, spending patterns and much more explored in this article. Navigating through the challenges, the new avenues and opportunities lie in the aftermath of the pandemic. In this article we try to understand the mindset and skill sets required to grab the jobs in the market and look into sectors flourishing in the face of such an event. Through statistics it is clear that there are many factors within the Covid-19 which are affecting jobs and job seekers.

Key words:

Introduction

Covid – 19 pandemic was an event unlike any the modern population has ever seen. Looking back it seems something out of science fiction. We currently are not even aware of what the long term effects of such an event will look like. While the short mid-term effects are showing right now with fragile economies, The effects of COVID-19 have been widespread and far-reaching. In terms of public health, the virus has claimed the lives of millions of people, with some countries experiencing exceptionally high death rates. It has also put a strain on healthcare systems as hospitals have been overwhelmed with patients, leading to shortages of supplies and personnel.

One of the most significant effects of COVID-19 has been the disruption of human life and social interactions. Governments around the world have implemented measures such as lockdowns, quarantines, and social distancing guidelines to try to slow the spread of the virus. These measures have resulted in the closure of schools, businesses, and public events, leading to a significant reduction in social interactions and a negative impact on mental health.

The economic impact of COVID-19 has also been significant. Many businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, have been forced to close or significantly reduce their operations, leading to widespread job losses and financial hardship. The global economy has been hit hard, with many experts predicting a long and difficult recovery process.

The impact of any disaster on economies always reflected on the work force and opportunities that are available to people at large. To better understand effects of this disease on the global economies and subsequently onto the job market a understanding of patterns is important. Before Covid-19 India had unemployment rate of 5.27% as reported by CEIC (CEIC, December 2019). In comparison to international unemployment rates for the developing and developed countries this data isn't out of the ordinary, but the data are maintained primarily by the government, but at the same time according to various reports the number was much higher in reality.

COVID -19 and Job Crisis

Covid-19 brought with it an economic downturn in all parts of the world with change in spending volumes and patterns almost overnight. The looming threat of huge medical expenses forced spenders to allocate their funds towards the essential items. Businesses had to do anything and everything to mitigate the losses posed and to stay afloat during this crisis. Many businesses have been forced to close or scale back operations, leading to widespread job losses and unemployment.

In the United States, the unemployment rate reached a high of 14.8% in April 2020, according to the Bureau of Labor Statistics. This was the highest rate since the Great Depression, and it has since come down to 6.7% as of September 2021. However, the pandemic has disproportionately affected certain industries and groups of workers, such as those in hospitality, retail, and the gig economy. Many of these workers have found it difficult to find new employment or have had to accept lower-paying jobs.

According to a report by the International Labour Organization (ILO), the pandemic could lead to the loss of 400 million jobs globally, with India being one of the worst affected countries. The lockdown measures implemented by the government have resulted in the closure of small businesses and reduced demand for goods and services, leading to job cuts and reduced working hours for many workers. The unemployment rate reached an all-time high of 7.11% in December 2020 according to CEIC Data.

The job crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has affected workers in nearly every industry, but some sectors have been hit harder than others. The hospitality and tourism industry, for example, has been particularly hard hit as travel restrictions and social distancing measures have led to a dramatic decline in demand. Retail, manufacturing, and the arts and entertainment sectors have also been heavily impacted.

The informal sector, which employs a large proportion of the Indian workforce, has been particularly hard hit. Evident by the mass labor migration who were relieved with basically no notice for an indefinite amount of time. The data for amount of people in this migration was conveniently not kept by any government body making it impossible to quantify the people impacted by this event. Many of these workers do not have any form of social security or unemployment benefits, and the pandemic has left them with no source of income. This has led to widespread poverty and hunger, with many people struggling to make ends meet.

The pandemic has also had an impact on the formal sector, with many companies opting for layoffs and salary cuts to stay afloat. This has led to a decline in the purchasing power of the middle class, which in turn has reduced demand for goods and services, further impacting the economy.

The government has implemented several measures to mitigate the impact of the pandemic on employment, such as providing financial assistance to small businesses and offering employment opportunities through schemes such as the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA). However, these measures have not been enough to fully address the job crisis in the country. This also had a ripple effect on other areas of the economy. Consumer spending, which drives economic growth, has decreased as people have less disposable income due to job losses or pay cuts. This has led to a slowdown in business activity and further job losses.

In addition to job losses, the COVID-19 pandemic has also led to a decrease in wages and hours for many workers. Many businesses have implemented pay cuts or reduced the hours of their employees in an effort to stay afloat during the crisis.

The job crisis caused by COVID-19 has also disproportionately affected certain groups of workers. For example, women, young workers, and low-wage workers have been more likely to lose their jobs or have their hours reduced. The pandemic has also had a disproportionate impact on minority and immigrant communities.

For the youth starting their careers at this time they were in for a different set of challenges. With job losses in abundance the supply of eligible and employable people without a job in most of sectors spiked add that with expensive Medicare was just the perfect storm for the job market. It propelled unemployment and desperation for jobs in the youth even higher. This consequently led to suddenly companies having an opportunity to get more work out of the job seekers with inappropriate payment.

At the same time the positive side of market shows that *“Even as India's job scenario continues to recover after seeing a sharp dip due to the coronavirus pandemic, the competition for finding jobs is higher than last year. The job scenario in the country saw a recovery at a 12 per cent year-on-year growth rate in August 2020, according to LinkedIn's labour market data. At the same time, the competition among professionals for jobs is 30 per cent higher than 2019. Meanwhile, nearly 3 in 5 or 62 per cent professionals in India are willing to pivot their careers to navigate these testing times, according to LinkedIn's Workforce Confidence Index findings. The data also shows that professionals from recreation and travel, retail, and corporate services are more likely to look for jobs outside their current industry”* (Business today 2020). While this was the trend in some sectors there is certainly a silver lining. Covid-19 gave a huge boost to remote jobs and companies and people alike found out that most of the roles could function remotely.

Conclusion and Way Forward

As we move ahead of COVID-19 pandemic many jobs seems to have gone back to the traditional office setup but there are still many that have embraced work from home and allow their employees to either work fully or partially from home. We have found new ways of doing business and that has opened up a plethora of new job opportunities.

India's service sectors which was already flourishing in export of commercial services having a global market share of 4.1% is expected to bounce back and some say even stronger as it carries 66% share in Indian GDP and generates 28% of the employment. Which is set to increase given the rise in tier – 2 and tier – 3 cities, in addition coming up with entrepreneurial ventures which further deepening the reach of service and product based businesses.

With people discovering the ways of working from home the major uptick has been seen in freelancer market and jobs catering internet businesses. Now to get these jobs up-skilling or learning a new skill can be done from the comforts of your homes with a wide library of paid and free courses available online.

In conclusion the setbacks of COVID-19 are plenty and are still unfolding with a lot of economies like China, Pakistan and Sri Lanka to name a few struggling. Indian economy seems to be faring better in comparison and is on the path to a slow but sure recovery. The choice of jobs and way of doing them is changing. A workforce who is young and ready to evolve certainly can prove to be best assets to the country, if its potential is going to be utilized optimally.

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